

Neutronic Study of Geometric Configurations of a Small Modular Molten Salt Reactor

Cuevas M¹, Lorduy-Alós M¹, da Silva C A M², Pereira C^{2*}, Gallardo S¹, Verdú G¹

¹Instituto Universitario de Seguridad Industrial, Radiofísica y Medioambiental, Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera, s/n, 46022 València, València, Spain

²Departamento de Engenharia Nuclear, Escola de Engenharia, Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Av. Antonio Carlos 6627, Campus Pampulha, Belo Horizonte, MG, Brazil

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a neutronic analysis of a thermal-spectrum small modular molten salt reactor (SM-MSR) core, comparing a standard single-channel design to a dual-channel configuration with varying fuel channel sizes. Both designs utilize a LiF-BeF₂-ThF₄-UF₄ fuel salt with a graphite moderator. Monte Carlo simulations with MCNP6 were used to evaluate core criticality (k_{eff}) and neutron flux distribution. The single-channel design, with a 2.0 cm fuel channel radius and 1.41% UF₄ in the salt, achieved a k_{eff} of 1.01279, indicating slightly supercritical operation and yielding a flat power profile across the core. The dual-channel design produced a more uniform neutron flux distribution but a lower k_{eff} (1.0009). These findings suggest that while the dual-channel core enhances flux uniformity, the single-channel design offers a superior reactivity margin and better neutron economy. Furthermore, the observed neutronic behavior indicates a high potential for passive safety based on the intrinsic characteristics of the thermal spectrum and the molten fuel.

Keywords: Small Modular Molten Salt Reactor (SM-MSR); Thorium fuel cycle; Dual-channel core configuration; Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the nuclear industry has shown a growing interest in Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) due to their potential for enhanced safety and reduced costs [1], [2]. The modularity of the SM-MSR is defined by three key strategic principles: factory-based manufacturing, transportability as a single pre-assembled unit, and scalability, which allows for incremental capacity additions to the power grid. Among the various SMR concepts, the Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) stands out for using liquid salts as fuel and coolant. This technology offers several advantages over traditional reactors, such as operation at higher temperatures and lower pressures, which improve thermodynamic efficiency and reduce risks associated with system pressurization [3], [4]. Furthermore, MSRs offer higher fuel burnup and the potential for continuous reprocessing, resulting in lower generation of long-lived radioactive waste [3], [4].

This study evaluates an SM-MSR based on the breeder concept employing the uranium–thorium (U–Th) fuel cycle. For this purpose, a model proposed in previous studies [5], [6] is adopted, as these references provide a detailed description of the reactor geometry and dimensions and demonstrate the computational feasibility required for performing neutronic simulations. The main goals of this work are to examine the effects of varying salt-to-fuel volume ratios (V_M/V_F) on reactor criticality optimization and to analyze alternative core configurations using MCNP6.2. The effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), neutron energy spectrum, and neutron flux distribution are the main parameters evaluated.

*claubia@nuclear.ufmg.br

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Reactor Design and Materials

The reactor under study is a thermal-spectrum Small Modular Molten Salt Reactor (SM-MSR) with a rated thermal power of 150 MW_t [5, 6]. The core uses a circulating fluoride salt mixture of lithium fluoride, beryllium fluoride, thorium fluoride, and uranium fluoride (LiF–BeF₂–ThF₄–UF₄) as fuel and coolant. This fuel salt is carried in an array of vertical channels within a graphite moderator matrix, and both the radial reflector and core internal structures are made of graphite. The fuel salt composition is based on the thorium/uranium fuel cycle. Initially, a low uranium content was assumed (on the order of 0.2% UF₄ in weight fraction in the salt, with the balance 12.3% ThF₄, 17.5% BeF₂, and 70% LiF). Lithium is highly enriched in ⁷Li (99.995%) to minimize parasitic neutron absorption, and the uranium is high-assay low-enriched uranium (HALEU) with 19.75% ²³⁵U. This enrichment level is critical for maintaining a compact modular core while optimizing the breeding of ²³³U from the ²³²Th fertile base. The structural material is Hastelloy-N, compatible with molten salts at 900 K, at which the fuel salt density is 3.30 g/cm³ and the graphite density is 2.30 g/cm³. Key design parameters are adopted from the reference SM-MSR described by Yu et al. (2023) and the thorium-fueled molten salt breeder reactor of Silva et al. (2024). In particular, the core's equivalent height is about 370 cm, and the overall radial build of the reactor follows Yu et al. (2023), from the center outward: an active fuel region, a graphite reflector, a structural barrel, an annular downcomer, and the reactor vessel. The total core and reflector radius is 170 cm, within an outer vessel radius of 178 cm. The active core region is a single-zone cylindrical volume with a radius of 130 cm and a height of 260 cm, filled with 241 fuel channels (graphite hexagonal prism elements, each containing a cylindrical fuel salt channel) arranged in a hexagonal lattice. Each fuel channel has an inner radius of $r = 2.0$ cm and is surrounded by graphite moderator within the hexagonal fuel element (pitch 15 cm). A graphite radial reflector, 50 cm thick, surrounds the core to reduce leakage and thermalize neutrons. Just outside the reflector is a 1 cm thick boron-carbide barrel, which provides structural support and additional neutron absorption. Beyond the barrel is a 4 cm thick downcomer region – an annular gap filled with circulating fuel salt (serving as coolant and providing a buffer to the vessel). The reactor vessel is 3 cm thick Hastelloy-N, providing the primary pressure boundary and serving as a gamma/neutron shield. No control rods are included in this neutronic model (consistent with many MSR designs in which reactivity is controlled by fuel chemistry or temperature feedback); the reference design likewise emphasizes intrinsic safety features over control rod insertion.

2.2. MCNP model

A three-dimensional Monte Carlo neutron transport model was developed using MCNP6 (version 6.2). The detailed core geometry was modeled explicitly: a single fuel channel (a graphite block with a cylindrical hole) was defined as a repeated universe element, and the full core was built by filling a large hexagonal lattice region with these channel universes. This approach leverages MCNP's repeated geometry capability to efficiently construct the 241-channel hexagonal array. The surrounding regions (reflector, barrel, downcomer, and vessel) were modeled as concentric cylindrical shells or rings, with the appropriate materials and thicknesses described above. Axial reflector regions (graphite above and below the active fuel region) and upper/lower plena were also included to match the 370 cm total height of the core assembly (Figure 1). Vacuum (absorbing) boundary conditions were applied at the outer surface of the vessel, while reflective boundary conditions were used at the top and bottom of the model to simulate an axially repeating geometry (since the core is effectively finite in height with physical reflectors, reflective boundaries at the ends were not used – instead, the actual graphite axial reflector and a small upper plenum were modeled explicitly). For criticality calculations, 115 neutron generations were simulated with 10,000 neutrons per generation, skipping the first 15 generations for equilibration (total 1,000,000 active histories).

Figure 1. Geometry of the MCNP model.

Material definitions for the salt include the appropriate isotopic fractions for Li (trace ${}^6\text{Li}$), Be, F, Th, and U. The initial heavy metal inventory corresponds to a thorium-heavy mixture with a fissile content in heavy metal of only 1.6% (consistent with a thorium breeder startup with mostly ${}^{233}\text{U}$ or ${}^{235}\text{U}$ as seed). This baseline composition was varied in a parametric study to find the uranium fraction needed for criticality in the smaller core. All calculations reported here assume the fuel salt is uniformly mixed and stationary (no flow or online reprocessing modeled) and at a uniform temperature of 900 K. Thermal neutron scattering treatments ($S(\alpha, \beta)$) for graphite were applied, and Doppler broadening at 900 K was used for all cross-sections. Because Monte Carlo tallies in a criticality calculation are given in arbitrary units (per source neutron), a normalization was applied to convert the results to absolute physical units corresponding to the reactor's power of 150 MW_{th}. A normalization methodology is adopted from Silva et al. (2024). In this approach, the normalization factor (neutron flux multiplier) is given by:

$$M_\phi = \frac{P \nu}{Q k_{\text{eff}}} \quad (1)$$

where P is the total thermal power (150 MW), ν is the fission rate (neutrons or fissions per second), and Q is the recoverable energy per fission event (considered $Q=200$ MeV). For this design, a value of $1.12 \cdot 10^{19}$ neutrons per second was obtained.

To explore the effect of core configuration on reactivity and flux, different moderator-to-fuel volume ratios are evaluated. In a single-channel design, the channel radius (smaller fuel channels yield a larger graphite volume fraction) determines the moderator-to-fuel volumetric ratio. This ratio is defined as $R = V_M/V_F$. R can be varied by changing the fuel channel radius (and adjusting the number of channels if needed). Guided by the reference design and parametric search, an optimal ratio around $R \approx 16.5$ is identified, achieved when $r = 2.0$ cm for the fuel channel radius.

2.3. Design Considering Two Different Fuel Channel Sizes

Additional simulations were performed with two fuel channel sizes (a two-zone core, with inner and outer regions) – those results are discussed later as a design alternative. All MCNP simulations, both for single-zone and two-zone configurations, utilized the same physics models and statistical settings as previously described. This second design considers two different sizes of fuel channels:

- Type 1 channel (inner), with radius r_1
- Type 2 channel (outer), with radius r_2 , where $r_2 > r_1$

Two distinct universes in MCNP are used to define the diameter of each channel type, with each associated with a specific volume. Figure 2 shows an example schematic of the core configuration. The values of r_1 and r_2 are calculated using the expressions presented (2-4), assuming as initial constants both the area ratio between channels of different sizes ($X = A_1/A_2$) and the volumetric ratio between the moderator and the fuel channel (V_M/V_F), based on the first design. Seven different configurations are studied, each characterized by a distinct number of channels of each type.

Figure 2. Proposed core configuration.

The ratio between the moderator volume and the fuel volume is a fundamental parameter in SMR design, whose configuration can be adapted to meet different energy applications. For a simplified design, considering a homogeneous cylindrical graphite core as moderator and cylindrical channels distributed radially as fuel regions, this ratio can be expressed as:

$$R = \frac{V_M}{V_F} = \frac{\pi r_N^2 \cdot h - n \cdot \pi r_N^2 \cdot h}{n \cdot r_N^2 \cdot h} \quad (2)$$

where R represents the ratio between the moderator volume (V_M) and the fuel volume (V_F), r_N is the core radius, r is the fuel channel radius, h is the core height, and n is the total number of channels. Simplifying the expression:

$$R = \frac{r_N^2}{n \cdot r_C^2} - 1 \quad (3)$$

For more complex configurations based on two different fuel channel sizes, the expression for the volume ratio is given as follows:

$$R = \frac{r_N^2 - n_1 r_1^2 - n_2 r_2^2}{n_1 r_1^2 + n_2 r_2^2} - 1 \quad (4)$$

where r_1 and r_2 are the radii of the smaller and larger fuel channels, respectively, and n_1 and n_2 represent the number of channels corresponding to each type.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Criticality and Neutronic Performance

It has been identified that a single-zone core configuration achieves effective criticality while maintaining a good neutron economy. The best-performing configuration consisted of a core with 241 identical fuel channels, each with a 2.0 cm radius, filled with fuel salt containing 1.41% UF₄ by mass. It corresponds to a uranium concentration just sufficient to reach criticality in the small core. The optimal single-zone configuration achieved a $k_{eff} = 1.01279 \pm 0.00061$ with 1.41% UF₄ by mass. This provides an excess reactivity of +1.28% $\Delta k/k$, sufficient to offset fuel depletion and fission-product poisoning during operation, as shown in Table I.

Table I. k_{eff} for different contains in UF₄ and channel radii.

Rad	$\frac{V_m}{V_f}$	0.2% UF ₄	1.0% UF ₄	1.25% UF ₄	1.38% UF ₄	1.41% UF ₄	1.5% UF ₄	2% UF ₄
1.0	69.1	0.21804	0.69419	0.78329	0.82510	0.83388	0.85868	0.97941
1.5	30.2	0.25988	0.81296	0.91162	0.95587	0.96601	0.99157	1.11408
2.0	16.5	0.28994	0.86524	0.96119	1.00390	1.01279	1.03904	1.15302
2.5	10.2	0.30390	0.87423	0.96433	1.00389	1.01209	1.03823	1.14350
3.0	6.8	0.30476	0.85432	0.93969	0.97429	0.98444	1.00609	1.10204
3.5	4.7	0.29814	0.81506	0.89361	0.92680	0.93374	0.95353	1.04155
4.0	3.4	0.28399	0.76350	0.83264	0.86293	0.86886	0.88790	0.96594
4.5	2.5	0.26566	0.69822	0.76001	0.78983	0.79347	0.80747	0.87848
5.0	1.8	0.24244	0.62649	0.68182	0.70536	0.70964	0.72313	0.78438
5.5	1.3	0.21622	0.55022	0.59777	0.61826	0.62343	0.63594	0.69360

Notably, this k_{eff} is in excellent agreement (within 0.11%) with the reference value reported by Silva et al. for a much larger thorium-based MSR ($k_{eff} = 1.01390 \pm 0.00062$). This agreement confirms that the small-core design can achieve the neutronic performance expected of a well-moderated thorium-fuel-cycle system. The slight positive reactivity margin (approximately $\rho = +0.0126$, or 1.26% in k units) provides operational flexibility for burnup and isotopic changes. It would be compensated for by inherent feedback or control mechanisms in practice. A reactivity excess of 1–2% is considered reasonable for startup; it can offset fuel depletion and fission product poisoning while remaining low enough to be managed safely. Table II summarizes the main neutronic parameters for the 2 cm and 1.41% UF₄ configurations, along with reference values from Silva et al. (2024) and the percent differences.

Table II. Summary of key neutronic parameters and comparison with reference models.

Parameter	MCNP6	Reference	Difference (%)
k_{eff}	1.01279 ± 0.00061	1.01390 ± 0.00062	0.1095
kP	1.00571 ± 0.00054	–	–
Λ (10 ⁻⁴ s)	7.4956 ± 0.0102	–	–
ν	2.428	–	–
η	1.2206	–	–
ρ	0.012628 ± 0.00061	0.01371 ± 0.00061	7.89
β_{eff}	0.00699	–	–

3.2. Neutron Flux Spatial and Energy Distribution

Figure 3a shows the radial neutron flux profile in the core for the 2 cm channel, 1.41% UF₄ case. The flux has been normalized to reactor power as described, so the values represent absolute neutron flux (in n/cm²·s) as a function of radius from the core center (0 cm) out to the reactor periphery. The radial flux profile is remarkably flat in the central 100 cm of the core, ensuring uniform power density. The neutron energy spectrum confirms the thermal nature of the reactor, with a strong peak around 10⁻⁷ MeV. It indicates a very uniform fission rate density in the fuel salt, a consequence of the high degree of moderation (abundant graphite) and the symmetric core configuration. Toward the outer core (approaching the graphite reflector at ~130–140 cm), the flux begins to fall off. At the core edge and beyond, a steady decline in flux is observed, dropping sharply through the reflector and shielding layers.

Figure 3. a) Radial neutron flux profile and b) Neutron energy spectrum.

The flux at the reactor vessel inner wall ($r \approx 178$ cm) is only a small fraction of the core flux (several orders of magnitude lower, as determined by the tallies), which is important for minimizing vessel irradiation. The plateau in the flux within the core indicates that power is evenly allocated among the fuel channels, a condition that improves thermal-hydraulic management by promoting relatively uniform graphite and fuel temperatures throughout the core and limiting the formation of hot spots. The slight dip in flux at the very center (if any) was negligible, implying no pronounced “over-moderation” in the core despite the large amount of graphite. The gradual flux decrease in the outer core is attributed to two factors: (1) the lower fuel channel density in the outermost rows (geometric edge effects where some volume is occupied by reflector rather than fuel), and (2) increased neutron leakage and absorption in the periphery (neutrons entering the reflector either return at reduced energy or are absorbed, and some leak out). These effects are inherent to the core geometry, and the reflector’s job is indeed to reflect some neutrons back – the results show that the reflector succeeds in sustaining flux up to the core boundary before the drop-off. Overall, the flux profile demonstrates that the single-zone core meets one key design goal: achieving uniform power distribution. Compared to a two-zone core with different channel sizes (examined in a later section), the single-channel design yields a more peaked flux in the center; however, in our case, the peak is essentially flat, so the benefit of moving to a two-zone design would be minor for flux shaping. In fact, the two-zone “optimal” design we studied achieved only a slightly more uniform profile at the expense of a lower k_{eff} (~1.0009), indicating a trade-off between reactivity and flux uniformity. For this discussion, we focus on the single-zone design as it provides the highest reactivity and already acceptable flux flatness.

The neutron energy spectrum in the core (Figure 3b) was tallied to confirm the thermal nature of the reactor and to identify the presence of any significant epithermal or fast neutron components. Figure 4b illustrates the normalized neutron flux as a function of energy, spanning from 10⁻⁸ MeV up to 10 MeV (plotted on a logarithmic energy scale). The neutron energy spectrum exhibits three distinct

regions characteristic of a well-thermalized system. In the thermal region ($<10^{-6}$ MeV), a strong peak appears around 10^{-7} MeV (~ 0.1 eV), indicating effective moderation by graphite. Most neutrons exist in this energy range, confirming a thermal-spectrum reactor where neutrons are slowed to near the 900 K Maxwellian peak. It ensures efficient fission of ^{235}U or ^{233}U and supports breeding from ^{232}Th . In the epithermal region (10^{-6} – 10^{-1} MeV), the flux decreases sharply, forming a valley that represents the rapid moderation process. Neutrons spend a short time in this interval, reflecting a high moderator-to-fuel ratio and efficient thermalization. In the fast region (>0.1 MeV), a small remaining flux corresponds to neutrons that have not been fully moderated or are newly born from fission. Although this component is much lower than the thermal flux, it contributes slightly to reactions such as (n,2n) or fast fission and causes most of the structural material damage. The design's B₄C barrel and graphite reflector effectively reduces this fast flux outside the core, protecting the reactor vessel and graphite components.

3.3. Implications for Core Design

Comparing the single-zone design to a potential two-zone (dual channel size) design provides insight into core optimization. In a two-zone core (inner region with smaller channels, outer with larger channels, as per Silva et al.), one can flatten the radial flux by intentionally under-moderating the inner core and over-moderating the outer core. Different design alternatives were proposed and found that indeed the radial flux slope can be minimized – for example, one configuration with inner channel radius 2 cm and outer channel radius ~ 3.46 cm (area ratio $X=3$) and with 15% of channels in the inner region yielded an almost flat flux profile across the core. However, that configuration's k_{eff} was about 1.0009, essentially critical but slightly lower than the single-zone's 1.0128. These results highlight a trade-off: introducing a second channel size (and thus a radially varying moderation ratio) can improve flux uniformity at the cost of reactivity. For a given total heavy metal inventory, the highest k_{eff} is obtained when all fuel sees the optimal moderation (in this case, $R\sim 16.5$ for both inner and outer regions), whereas flattening the flux requires deviating from that optimum in parts of the core (inner zone more thermalized, outer zone less, or vice versa).

The single-zone design already had a fairly uniform flux, so the benefit of two zones was marginal. Therefore, it is considered that the single-channel design (2 cm radius channels, uniform lattice) is the preferred choice for this 150 MWt SM-MSR, as it maximizes neutron economy and simplicity while still maintaining an acceptable power profile. If operational considerations demand an even flatter power distribution (for example, to minimize graphite temperature gradients at higher power), a two-zone approach could be implemented with a slight enrichment or fuel loading adjustment to regain lost reactivity (Figure 4a and 4b).

Figure 4. a) Radial neutron flux profile and b) k_{eff} for the different salt-to-fuel ratios and core configurations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The neutronic analysis demonstrates that the 150 MWt SM-MSR core can achieve criticality with a stable thermal spectrum and uniform flux distribution using HALEU fuel. These preliminary results suggest that the system possesses favorable neutronic characteristics for passive safety, although definitive validation requires further studies on temperature reactivity feedback and dynamic shutdown margins. The single-channel design is the preferred configuration for modular deployment due to its simplicity and superior neutron economy compared to dual-channel alternatives. The MCNP6 Monte Carlo results provide detailed confidence in the design's neutronic performance: a critical k_{eff} with minimal excess, a strongly thermal spectrum, and a uniform flux (power) profile. These features imply that the reactor will have good safety characteristics (a large negative temperature coefficient expected from the thermal spectrum and graphite moderation) and efficient fuel utilization (thanks to the high level of thermal neutron absorption in thorium and sufficient η to breed new fuel). The comparison with literature values (Yu et al., 2023; Silva et al., 2024) shows excellent agreement, lending validation to our modeling approach. These results support the feasibility of the core design and provide a baseline for further optimization.

If needed, design adjustments such as introducing multiple channel sizes or slight changes in fuel loading can be made to tune the flux distribution or reactivity margin, thereby meeting specific engineering criteria (e.g., material limits or burnup targets). Overall, the observed neutronic behavior suggests that this SM-MSR configuration is a promising candidate for a safe, reliable, and efficient small modular reactor that leverages the thorium fuel cycle.

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